

THE ROLE OF DJADIDS' IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK TERMINOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8074441>

Abstract

The article presents views on the development of the Uzbek terminological lexicon, its periodization, and showing its chronological evolution. Linguists and terminologists have carried out periodization of the development of the Uzbek literary language and, on this basis, its terminology, and it is noted that the era of the modern enlighteners should be highlighted, and this view is proved based on the terminological approaches of the moderns. The opinions of the famous Jadids Fitrat, Elbek, Ashurali Zahiri and Husayn Khan regarding the acquisition of the term and the creation of a new term are explained through examples.

Keywords: terminology, Uzbek terminology, periodization of the development of terminology, djadids', "Chig'atoy gurungi", Fitrat, Elbek, Ashurali Zohiriy, "Sarf", "Nahv"

Introduction

When researching the lexical system of a certain period, in particular, its terminology, it is first necessary to study the development of the lexicon of the language to which this system belongs. The reason is that the lexical system is more dynamic and variable than other parts of the language.

During the development of a particular language, its vocabulary (vocabulary, including terminology) undergoes rapid, significant and serious changes compared to other areas. There are objective, socio-political reasons for this, of course. These changes reflect the development of vocabulary and terminology not only quantitatively, but also qualitatively. [Madvaliyev, 2017]

When it comes to the development of the Uzbek terminological lexicon, it is important to periodize it and show its chronological evolution. In this sense, the development of the Uzbek literary language and its terminology were carried out by linguists and terminologists. Although these periodic indicators are reasonable and appropriate, they do not include the "modern era" as a separate stage. This period is usually studied as part of the Uzbek terminology of the Jadids period. However, in our opinion, the period of the Jadids should be singled out as a separate period in the development of terminology. The reason is that their terminological (term perception, formation of a term system, spelling of terms) views served as the basis for the formation of Uzbek terminology as a separate area.

A new era of linguistic terminology

In the first quarter of the 20th century, issues of terminology, in particular term selection, introduction of scientific terms into the system of sciences developed rapidly. During this period, units of scientific methods took on a special national character, and a Turkic approach

to the use of terms appeared. This situation, of course, is related to the activities of modern enlighteners. The establishment of "Chigatoy Gurungi", the opening of new method schools, the establishment of the press - all this led to a sharp increase in news in the terminological system of the Uzbek language. A number of terminological systems were formed, such as pedagogical terminology of the Uzbek language, terms of literary studies and linguistics, journalistic terms.

The scientific study of the Uzbek language began with Fitrat's works "Sarf" and "Nahv" and the activity of "Chigatoy Gurungi" led by him. During this period, there were also disputes about linguistic terms. Some experts are in favor of using Arabic, Persian and Russian terms, while others are in favor of Uzbekization of such terms. [Ermatorov, 2019]

Materials and Methods

The work of Fitrat and Elbek is of particular importance in solving the problem. In modern Uzbek linguistics, "vowels" are represented by the term "chozgi" in the works of Fitrat. Researchers focused on the length of vowels and used the term length. In addition, Elbek's scientific observations also used the terms "sound letter, phoneme". By 1926, the use of the term vowel, which is still used today, became official. At the same time, an attempt was made to create a term based on the internal capabilities of the Uzbek language. In particular, the terms "tovushli (tovishli), unsiz (tovushsiz)" were the first alternatives to the terms "vowel and consonant", which were later changed. At that time, there was no term "syntax" to describe a branch of grammar. "Nahv" is one of the first terms as the name of a section of grammar, in which "clause, participle, possessive, determiner, introductory word, colon" and others are used. This textbook also contains the terms nahv (sintaksis), kelishkanlik (moslashuv), eksik gap (atov gap) that are not used now. When we looked at the work done on Fitrat's notes and his scientific heritage, we were drawn to the scientist's thoughts not only on linguistic terms, but also on theoretical issues of terminology. In particular, Fitrat's views on language development have not lost their relevance even for modern terminology.

Fitrat elaborates on the laws of language development and word acquisition in his work "Rules of Literature". In his opinion, the main factor in the development of national languages is the creation of new words based on the capabilities of each language. New concepts that have emerged in social life should be expressed with their own elements of the national language as much as possible. As new concepts are formed, finding new words and new forms to express them is the best way to enrich languages in this way. Such new artificial words, created based on the national nature of the language, which fully correspond to the internal laws of that language, serve to preserve the purity and nationality of the language.

Another way to develop languages is that if it is not possible to express a new concept through the capabilities of the national language, it is necessary to borrow words from other languages. Learning in this way serves the development of national languages. The acquired word should be adapted as much as possible to the national nature of this language - the system of sounds, grammatical rules. At this point, it is appropriate to use the term "sarf qoidalari" mentioned by Fitrat as an example. The scientist recommends the use of the compound "qavaida sarfiya" in this way. Even though the lexical change did not occur in the above example, a morphological and syntactic change occurred in the compound. In other

words, the compound was Uzbekized morphologically and syntactically, subjected to the laws of our language [Qurbanova, 1997]

Discussion

The same situation, i.e., the issue of adaptation of acquired terms to the internal capabilities of the language, was also reflected in the leadership of Ashurali Zahiri. The scientist pays special attention to the purity of the language when he stops at the issue of terms. He points out that the literary language should be freed from foreign terms as much as possible, and only if such words are not in our language, words should be borrowed first from the sister Turkic languages, and then from other languages. [Togayev, 2020] Ashurali Zahiri condemns unnecessary or forced borrowing of terms from other languages. In fact, the purity of the language, especially the preservation of the purity of the units (terms) of the scientific method, has been considered one of the urgent problems in all times. The reason is that scientific method units - terms, especially if they are related to a new field, science, quickly change to the language of society, although in essence there is an alternative, the term is left as it is. This legality of terminology was noted during the above comments of A. Zahiri. "Inherited Persian" (obdasta, kafgir, kambag'al, darvish...), "popularized Arabic" (maktab, kitob, qalam, hukumat...) and Russian-international related to the political and philosophical sphere (dynamo, volt, radio, meter...) recommends leaving the words as they are. He suggests that some terms transferred from European languages can be expressed in the national language. For example, instead of the word astronomiya, it is necessary to use terms such as yulduz biligi (astro-yulduz, nomiya-bilig), water knowledge instead of suv biligi, o'simlik biligi instead of botany, and ekin bilgich instead of agronomist. Also, Ashurali Zahiri offers to establish a special terminology commission under the Scientific Center under the Education Commissariat. A number of tasks of this commission, in particular, the commission and its employees often go to the districts and villages where the industry is developed and search for words from the people's language. and determines the framework of exchange of experience.

It is known that the period of writing based on Arabic and Latin graphics includes the years 1920-1940 and is characterized by the creation of rather simple textbooks and manuals from the native language, and the linguistic terms have not yet been completely stabilized. [Ermatov, 2019] Nevertheless, famous terminographers [Madvaliyev, 2017] explain the initial stage of the development of Uzbek language terminology with the years 1920-1930. The reason is that during this period, issues of language and terminology cause discussions and disputes between different groups with opposing views. These debates and controversies will be resolved at the language-spelling conference held in Samarkand in May 1929*

The decisions of the conference indicated two sources of further enrichment of the Uzbek language and terminology, i.e., the Uzbek language's own capabilities and the Russian-international fund.

The Language and Terminology Committee under the People's Commissariat of Education of Uzbekistan (1929-1933), the Central New Alphabet and Terminology Committee under the Central Executive Committee of Uzbekistan (1933-1938) and some experts played a major role in the formation and development of Uzbek scientific terminology. .

Conclusions

As you can see, the Jadids' contribution to the development of science and education, journalism, art, politics, and language is significant in scope and significance. These aspects are expressed in publications, works, in particular, in the terms and terminological views used in them.

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